

References

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Chemical Examination of Stem Bark of *Ficus infectoria* Roxb.

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FICUS infectoria Roxb. (Moraceae) is widely distributed in plains and lower hills of India. The stem bark of the plant is used^{1,2} in the indigenous system of medicine in the treatment of various diseases. We now report the isolation of some acetates of long-chain alcohols, methyl ricinolate, β -sitosterol, lanosterol, caffeic acid, bergenin and some sugars.

Experimental

The powdered stem bark was Soxhleted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and alcohol (95%). The petroleum ether extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and chromatographed over neutral alumina. Elutions were carried out with petroleum ether and its mixture with benzene furnished the compounds A, B, C and D.

Compound A: Elution with petroleum ether yielded a white solid (MeOH : EtOAc), m.p. 60–70°. Tlc examination showed it to be a mixture of four components. The glc and mass spectra^{3,4} revealed these as n-tetracosyl acetate (M^+ 396, 37.1%), n-hexacosyl acetate (M^+ 424, 15.5%), n-octacosyl acetate (M^+ 452, 41.2%) and n-triacontyl acetate (M^+ 480, 6.2%) respectively. The identity of the esters was further confirmed by their isolation and spectral analyses.

Compound B: Further elution with petroleum ether gave a yellow oily liquid, b.p. 227–28°/15 mm, identified as methyl ricinolate by chemical and spectral (ir⁵, pmr⁶, mass⁷) analyses and hydrolysis to the corresponding acid (ricinoleic acid).

Compound C: The petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 1) elution yielded colourless plates (MeOH), m.p. 138°; positive Liebermann–Burchard and TNM test; the acetate, m.p. 121–22°. Identification of the compound as β -sitosterol was made

through comparison of m.m.p., co-tlc, ir and pmr spectra.

Compound D: The eluate of petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 3) furnished colourless crystals (MeOH–Me₂CO), m.p. 141–42°; positive Liebermann–Burchard and TNM test; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 420, 1 040 (OH) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=C). The pmr and mass spectral data identified it as lanosterol which was further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc with authentic sample⁸ and preparation of the acetate, m.p. 132–33°.

The alcoholic extract on concentration under reduced pressure deposited KCl crystals. The mother liquor was reduced to red-brown syrupy mass and divided into methanol soluble and insoluble fractions. The methanol soluble part when chromatographed over silica gel, furnished the compounds E and F.

Compound E: Elution with EtOAc–MeOH (2 : 1) afforded yellow needles, m.p. 208–10°; positive TNM test; decolourised bromine and KMnO₄ solutions; green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 220, 230sh, 285 and 325 nm. Its ir data revealed it to be caffeic acid which was further confirmed by preparation of the diacetate, m.p. 189–90° and the methyl ester, m.p. 151–52°.

Compound F: The eluate with EtOAc–MeOH (1 : 3) was crystallised as colourless crystals (MeOH), m.p. 236–37°, C₁₄H₁₆O₉ (M^+ 328); red colour with aqueous FeCl₃. It was identified as bergenin by comparison of its uv, ir, pmr and mass spectra with the reported data^{9,10} and preparation of the pentaacetate, m.p. 201–02°.

The methanol-insoluble part (water-soluble) gave positive Molisch test, and when subjected to ascending paper chromatography it revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose. The identity was further confirmed by co-pc with authentic samples.

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